

SELF-REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES: BLENDS OF THERMOPLASTIC AND THERMOTROPIC LIQUID CRYSTALLINE POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

Blends based on PC/PET-PHB60 and Ultem/K161 have been studied in order to verify the effect of the addition of low amount of a liquid crystalline polymer on the rheological and mechanical properties of the thermoplastic matrices.

INTRODUCTION

Improving of physical properties of polymers can usually be obtained by the addition of fillers to a polymeric matrix. In fact, compounding of reinforcing materials, as graphite and glass fibers, with thermoplastic or thermosetting matrices can lead to composites with high mechanical strength and stiffness, good environmental resistance, high dimensional stability and so forth. However, the presence of a solid phase during the processing operations increases the viscosity of the system. Raising the temperature to reduce the viscosity can cause the thermal degradation of the polymeric matrix. Moreover, the large energy required will increase the costs of the final articles. Other problems that can rise from the inclusion of solid fibers are the difficulty in achieving a uniform dispersion of the reinforcing phase, wearing of the surfaces in relative motion of the processing machinery, and breakage of the fibers during the processing operations. In order to overcome these difficulties the so called "in situ" composites have recently attracted the interest of the scientific and industrial world. In such a class of materials the reinforcing filler is not present as a solid phase during the processing operations but it develops when the polymers and the second phase are cooled to the solid state. The term "in situ" composite is related, in fact, to the "in situ" shaping of the reinforcing filler. Among the different approaches used in this direction so far, the most effective in coupling the mentioned advantages achievable in traditional composites (i.e. improving of mechanical properties of the unfilled polymers) with an easier processability of the composites themselves has been the use of thermotropic liquid crystalline polymers (TLCP) as reinforcing phase (1). These materials, in fact, consist of rigid backbone molecules spaced with flexible groups in order to make their processability easier (2). The liquid crystalline polymers structure is based on domains in which the chain molecules are fairly parallel. In absence of external constraints the directors of the liquid crystalline domains are randomly oriented, while they easily orient along the fiber axis when the polymer is uniaxially stretched at the temperature of mesophase existence. Due to the high relaxation time of these materials compared to that of traditional isotropic polymers, the TLCP retain the fibrillar structure in the solid state, when the materials is cooled. As a result, the extruded and the melt drawn articles are characterized by a highly anisotropic structure responsible for the high rigidity values. Moreover, a sharp reduction in viscosity occurs for the

anisotropic melt. This event was ascribed by Wissburn (3) to the assumption that the rigid rods in TLCP will easily line up when sheared, thereby reducing the resistance to flow. Thermoplastic polymers are, therefore, expected to show an easier processability if a low amount of TLCP is added as a second phase and the processing operations are carried out in the temperature range of mesophasic behavior of the TLCP. In addition, the TLCP molecules, included in the isotropic matrix, if oriented in the flow field, can improve the rigidity of the unfilled polymer, acting as a reinforcing agents in composites. In this work the behavior of the isotropic matrices (Polycarbonate (PC) and Polyimide (Ultem)) modified by two different TLCP's has been analyzed. In particular, the two different matrices used in this study cover two different ranges of processability. While PC is, in fact, a traditional thermoplastic, Ultem belongs to the class of the so called "engineering plastics", high heat resistance materials whose processability shows serious difficulties.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amorphous matrices used in this work are the bisphenol-A-polycarbonate, PC, commercialized as Lexan, and a polyetherimide, known as Ultem, both produced by General Electrics.

The liquid crystalline polymers utilized are the poly(ethylene terephthalate-co-p-oxybenzoate (PET-PHB60) produced by Tennessee Eastman Kodak Company and provided by Dr. Jackson, and the fully aromatic polyester kindly provided by Bayer Company and here reported as K161.

The materials were vacuum dried at 110°C for 10 hours before mixing. The blending of Polycarbonate with PET-PHB60 was performed using a single-screw Haake extruder at T=240°C and 32 rpm to produce a strand that was chopped into pellets. The Ultem/K161 blends were prepared by means of a Brabender equipped with a mixing chamber at the temperature of 340°C at 32 rpm. Blends were prepared in both cases with compositions ranging from 5 to 50 % w/w of TLCP in the amorphous matrices. They will be referred as PC/PET-PHB60 95/5, Ultem/K161 95/5 and so forth, where the numbers identify the matrix and the TLCP percentages respectively.

A differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) Mettler TA3000 system was used to evaluate the transition temperatures of the parent polymers and of the blends. The temperature range investigated was from 0 to 500°C at a single scanning rate of 10°C/min.

Rheological measurements in the high shear rate region were carried out by the aid of a capillary viscometer (Rheoscope 1000, Ceast). The behavior at low shear rates has been studied in some cases too. A Rheometrics Mechanical Spectrometer (RMS) was used. The rheological measurements were performed at the temperatures of 220, 240, 260°C for PC/PET-PHB60 system and at the temperatures of 310, 330, 350°C for the Ultem/K161 system.

Spinning of the pure polymers, the PC/PET-PHB60 90/10 and Ultem/K161 90/10 and 70/30 was performed by means of the Rheoscope 1000 provided with a melt-spinning unit using a die of D=1 mm and a L/D ratio of 10. The extrusion rate was in all cases approximately 45 cm/min. The filaments were collected in air at room temperature on a 8 cm diameter bobbin at a distance of about 30 cm from the die exit. The take-up velocity was varied in order to obtain V_f/V_0 (draw ratio) values included between 10 and 300. The true draw ratio values were determined from the ratio between the die and fiber cross section (S_0/S_f) measured by an optical microscope.

The morphology of the TLCP's and of the blends processed under shear (from the capillary rheometer) and elongational (drawn fibers) flow conditions was analyzed by means of a scanning electron microscope (SEM), Cambridge Stereoscan 100. The fracture surfaces were obtained in liquid nitrogen. Moreover, the PC and Ultem matrices were dissolved in chloroform and methylene chloride respectively and the remaining TLCP phase was analyzed by means of an optical microscope, Polyvar by Reichert-Jung, under cross polarizers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The DSC thermogram of as received PET-PHB60 and PC are reported in Fig.1a. The TLCP, whose block configuration has been already reported by several authors (4), shows a first glass transition temperature (T_g) at 72°C, associated to the phase rich in polyethyleneterephthalate, while the second one at 172°C, is related to the T_g of a PHBA rich phase. The small and very broad peak at T=245°C is ascribed to the melting of small amounts of the crystalline phase. The isotropization of the material occurs at T=450°C. The DSC thermogram of PC shows a T_g of 145°C. In Fig.1b the thermograms of the fully aromatic TLCP by Bayer (K161) and of the Ultem are reported. The

former shows a first T_g in correspondance of about 118°C and a second T_g at 279°C. No melting peaks are detectable, while the isotropization occurs at 466°C. The latter shows a T_g at 214°C.

Fig.1 DSC thermograms of: a) PC and PET-PHB60, b) Ultem and K161

The processability temperatures of the two amorphous matrices analyzed are in completely different ranges. The liquid crystalline polymer to be used as a second phase, therefore, is related to the thermal behavior of PC and Ultem. The PET-PHB60, in fact, shows the nematogenic (liquid crystalline) characteristics in the temperature range of processability of PC, while for the K161 the mesophasic behavior is present at the Ultem higher processing temperature. In particular, for this material the necessity to depress the very high processing temperature is the primary problem to be solved.

In Fig.2 the DSC thermograms of two different blends are reported. In both cases no appreciable variations in the T_g's of the matrices are detectable, i.e. in both cases the TLCP's and the amorphous polymers are substantially incompatible. This means that the TLCP segregates as a second phase in the host matrix.

Fig.2 DSC thermograms of: PC/PET-PHB60 90/10, Ultem/K161 70/30

The flow curves of PET-PHB60 and K161 at different temperatures are reported in Fig.3a and 3b respectively.

Fig.3 Viscosity vs. shear rate at different temperatures for: a) PET-PHB60 at $T=220^{\circ}\text{C}$ (+), $T=240^{\circ}\text{C}$ (*), $T=270^{\circ}\text{C}$ (✱), b) K161 at $T=300^{\circ}\text{C}$ (o), $T=315^{\circ}\text{C}$ (✱), $T=330^{\circ}\text{C}$ (+), $T=350^{\circ}\text{C}$ (*).

In both cases, in the shear rate range investigated, the viscosity continuously shear thins. Blending of these materials with the thermoplastics gives rise to the rheological behavior reported in Fig.4a and 4b. In particular for the PC/PET-PHB60 system (Fig.4a) the viscosity data reported, taken at $T=240^{\circ}\text{C}$, cover a range of five decades of shear rates from 10^{-2} to 10^3 s^{-1} . The PC exhibits a typical Newtonian flow behavior at the low shear rates investigated, while it shows a tendency to shear thin if subjected to high shear rates. The same flow trend is shown by the blends with the lower content of TLCP. On the other hand, at higher contents of mesophasic polymer ($\sim 50 \text{ w/w}$) the rheology of the blend is strongly affected by the second phase, whose viscosity, as pointed out above, continuously shear thins in the range investigated. Similar considerations can be applied to the Ultem/K161 system (Fig.4b), whose viscosity data were taken at $T=330^{\circ}\text{C}$. In both cases viscosity values for all the blends were found to lie between those of the parent polymers.

Fig.4 Viscosity vs. shear rate for: a) PC (Δ), PC/PET-PHB60 95/5 (∇), 90/10 (\diamond), 50/50 (\square), PET-PHB60 (o) at $T=240^{\circ}\text{C}$, b) Ultem (+), Ultem/K161 95/5 (x), 90/10 (o), 70/30 (*), K161 (✱) at $T=330^{\circ}\text{C}$

The dependence of viscosity (η) on the composition of the blend is reported in Fig.5a and 5b where η is plotted vs. the TLCP percent at different values of shear rates ($\dot{\gamma}$). In the case of the PC/PET-PHB60 blend, whose data were taken also at the lower $\dot{\gamma}$, the viscosity increases with TLCP content in correspondence of $\dot{\gamma}$ up to $3 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, as expected since in this region the PET-PHB60 represents the more viscous component in the blend. At the higher values of $\dot{\gamma}$ both systems show a decrease of η increasing with the content of TLCP in the blend. A significant drop of about 30% in the

viscosity occurs at 5% TLCP, and it becomes 50% at 10% of TLCP.

Fig.5 Viscosity vs TLCP percentage at different shear rates for: a) PC/PET-PHB60 system at $T=240^{\circ}\text{C}$, b) Ultem/K161 system at $T=330^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fibers of PET-PHB60 were spun at $T=260^{\circ}\text{C}$, while fibers of K161 were spun at $T=330^{\circ}\text{C}$. The values of the elastic modulus vs. draw ratio for the Eastman Kodak TLCP are reported in a previous paper (5), while Fig.6 shows the corresponding data for the Bayer TLCP. In both cases the modulus sharply increases with S_0/S_f changing from the values of 2.4 and 5 GPa of the simple extruded ($S_0/S_f=1$) PET-PHB60 and K161 respectively, to values of about 30 GPa at the higher draw ratios. In particular for K161 the maximum draw ratio reached was only ~ 50 , lower than the values of 300 obtained in the case of the Kodak TLCP. The more rigid structure of K161 TLCP may be responsible for the initial higher modulus of the extruded Bayer TLCP (i.e. the relaxation time is higher and so the material retains more orientation) and for the lower draw ratio obtained. In both cases the directors of the nematic domains randomly distributed in the quiescent state, easily orient along the fiber axis when the polymer is uniaxially stretched at the temperature of mesophase existence. A fibrillar structure is therefore obtained at the higher S_0/S_f values used, as confirmed both by SEM and X-Ray analysis performed on the PET-PHB60 (5), and by SEM in the case of K161. The SEM micrography of a K161 fiber drawn at $T=330^{\circ}\text{C}$ with $S_0/S_f \sim 50$ is reported in Fig.7 and shows the fibrillar nature of this material.

Fig.6 Elastic modulus (E) vs draw ratio (S_0/S_f) for K161 fibers drawn at 370°C

Fig.7 SEM of K161 fiber drawn at $T=370^{\circ}\text{C}$ with $S_0/S_f=40$

The addition of 10% w/w of PET-PHB60 to the PC slightly modifies the elastic modulus vs. draw ratio trend of the PC matrix if the spinning operations were carried out at the temperature of 260°C . On the other hand, the blend tensile modulus increased of 50% compared to that of PC if the fibers were spun at 210°C . In table 1 the temperature of processing and the elastic modulus for the PC/PET-PHB60 system, elsewhere reported (6), are related

TABLE 1

Material	Drawing temperature	E' (GPa)
PC	260°C	2.7
PC blend 90/10	260°C	3
PC	210°C	3.1
PC blend 90/10	210°C	4.4

The different blend morphology obtained at the different drawing conditions could account for the different mechanical behavior above described. The scanning electron micrography of the transversal section of the samples processed at the higher temperature revealed droplet-like TLCP regions in the PC matrix (6). The second phase, therefore, did not elongate during the drawing process and the modulus of the thermotropic particles in the composite could be assumed similar to that of the unoriented TLCP, which in turn is not different from the PC modulus. No reinforcing effect on the rigidity of the matrix could be expected in this case. If the blend is drawn at $T=210^{\circ}\text{C}$ the TLCP phase elongates and a reinforcing effect could be justified on the basis of the Halpin-Tsai composite theory (7)

In the case of Ultem/K161 system drawing was performed at $T=330^{\circ}\text{C}$. Blends with compositions of 10% and 30% of TLCP in Ultem were analyzed and the moduli values vs. S_0/S_f are reported in Fig.8a and 8b.

Fig.8 Elastic modulus (E) vs. draw ratio (S_0/S_f) for: a) Ultem (○) and Ultem/K161 90/10 (+), b) Ultem (○) and Ultem/K161 70/30 (+). Drawing temperature = 330°C

It must be pointed out that the modulus of the stiff Ultem polyetherimide increases with increasing draw ratio. The addition of a low amount of TLCP, therefore, may only slightly improve the matrix behavior (Fig.8a), even if the TLCP presents a fiber like structure shape revealed by the optical analysis performed on the K161 after the matrix was dissolved (Fig.9a). If 30% of K161 is added as a second phase the modulus of the blend notably increases compared to that of the modulus of the unfilled matrix. The plateau values, in fact, changed from the value of ~ 3.5 GPa for Ultem to the value of ~ 6.5 GPa for the Ultem/K161 70/30 blend. The optical micrographs reported in Fig.9b shows, in fact, K161 fibers characterized by a high aspect ratio.

Fig.9 Optical Micrographs for K161 fibers after dissolution of the Ultem matrix for blends: a) Ultem/K161 90/10, b) Ultem/K161 70/30. Drawing temperature = 330°C .

CONCLUSIONS

Many advantages can be derived from the blending of thermotropic liquid crystalline polymers (TLCP) with polycarbonate (PC) and polyetherimide (Ultem). In fact, the addition of a thermotropic polymer reduces the shear viscosity of the matrix during the processing operations. In general, mechanical properties of the so formed in situ composite were found superior to those of the unfilled thermoplastic. Moreover, the existence of two distinct phases, the possibility of orienting the thermotropic polymer during the processing and the stability of the liquid crystalline

phase are necessary conditions in order to improve the mechanical properties of the resulting composites.

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